

ENABLERS FOR THE INDUSTRIALIZATION OF INFUSION PROCESSES: MERGING RESEARCH AND APPLICATION DRIVEN EXPECTATIONS

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EXTENDED ABSTRACT

For industrial process, high availability and robustness are required. The significant amount of manual works, as well as the diversity of infusion processes, drastically reduces the probability to introduce them into industrial environment.

The aim of this contribution is to present and to describe some needs from industrial point of view, which could be subjected of applied research works. A total of 3 main topics (so called enablers), explicitly the mastering of process complexity, the modelling & simulation capabilities and the monitoring capabilities, are discussed. The topics are illustrated by examples derived mostly from previous developments. The discussion of each aspect is completed by the highlight of the expected benefit for the industrial application of infusion processes. The examples have been selected with respect to the criticality of the considered process step for the overall performance of the process chain. This paper is not intended to describe the large family of infusion processes; for more information on such processes, the reader must refer to the common literature.

The three enablers identified are summarized in the following paragraphs.

Process complexity to be mastered

Current industrial challenges for the serial application of infusion processes require the capability to design robust process. The robustness is not only defined with respect to the repeatability, but also to the sizing and tuning capability. While the sizing is related to the reliable handling of various part size and complexity, the tuning capability represents a major criteria for serial production. The tuning capability must fulfil the aptitude to ramp-up but also to ramp-down the productivity. Such a capability assumes that the methods and the tools being used are applicable to various work-share configurations. This requirement becomes critical for infusion processes since they involve various types of constraints such as infusion time, shift models, logistics etc.

A methodology to proper size infusion processes with respect to length and time dimensions is therefore an enabler for the assessment of the industrialization of any given production scenario involving infusion processes.

The proper sizing of all auxiliary materials represents a further enabler for the industrialization of infusion processes. Due to the large variety of materials and properties needed, it is no rare to face

mismatching combination resulting into low maturity of the infusion processes. As for example, the selection of flow enhancement layers or the usage of a semipermeable membrane are decisions made only with respect to specific but temporally functionalities compares to the entire process duration. The thermal behaviour of such materials is usually not investigated and the impact on the resulting part quality not explicitly traced. The complex and random handling of such materials, the efforts needed for the demoulding and the related working time are aspects with negative impact on the introduction of infusion processes into serial production. The usage of so called infusion-kits can be considered as an enabler for higher maturity, which is mandatory to success with infusion processes.

Modelling and simulation capabilities

Meta modelling capabilities are required in order to use the simulation at earlier stage of the process design: the designation “meta-modelling” is used here to describe the ability to define the granularity of the model on a customized way, by keeping the balance between modelling effort (time, cost) and the maturity level of the entire development. Most of the time, infusion simulation is launched very early on a naive way and results either into a never ending story or into a serious disappointment with respect to the ratio between expectations and efforts. For industrial applications, models and tools dealing with uncertainties are intended to be more useful and powerful at earlier development stages rather than models and tools based on highly accurate models (identifiable though the large amount of needed input) but with limited aptitude to represent all involved system properties (only focussed on a few physics field). A resin flow simulation capable to handle the intrinsic flow behaviour based on the percentage distribution of fibre orientation and the average weight per square meter of a given fibrous reinforcement would be more powerful and suitable to accelerate the first down-selection of manufacturing process type and to earlier influence the tool and the part design than the current ones. By doing so, the opportunity to integrate critical manufacturing constraints into the design loop must be given. Such a contribution of the process simulation generate a higher value than the conventional fire-fighting mode being observed everywhere: It must not be longer the intention of the virtual prediction, to calibrate the model according to the outcome from the critical validation test.

Especially for infusion and injection simulation, capabilities to simulate the direct environment of the fibrous reinforcement must help to close the gap between reality and lab conditions. As illustrative example, the system preform-tool cavity is considered. The purpose is to show how the simulation of the real flow behaviour based on the usage of Neuman-like boundary condition for the pressure field could be achieved. Additionally to the detection of possible secondary injection points, the example also illustrates the influence of the too stiffness on the flow front evolution.

More multi-physics should contribute to provide more reliable predictions and to identify secondary effects not considered before. Furthermore, the ability to simulate concurrent fields could be the step maker for the realistic prediction of non-quality and for the formulation of their evolution laws.

The combination of fracture flow modelling approaches with the Darcy law can also be cited as enabler to link the process simulation to real flow conditions.

By doing so, one can take into account the local variation of proper flow behaviour (i.e. the shear stress) according to the complexity and to the size of the domain being impregnated, without loss of the integrity of the information one is focussed on.

Monitoring capabilities

Process monitoring as enabler to detect but also to prevent manufacturing defects.

Since infusion processes exhibit a high amount of hazardous steps with respect to the process robustness and reproducibility, monitoring solutions capable to track not only the detailed field variables (such as flow front position, temperature, pressure, viscosity etc.) but also to monitor the dynamic behaviour of the entire system could contribute to design and deploy real industrial infusion processes, that is, processes subjected to online pro-active control and readjustment. An illustrative example dealing with the non-immersive monitoring of the flow front evolution is proposed. The idea consists into the correlation of the real-time detection of the flow front contour (based on digital image

processing) with well-defined flow patterns, which were derived from preliminary tests and qualified as stable configuration. Alternatively, the flow pattern can also be derived from a reliable simulation. This approach can be completed by the philosophy of data fusion: since the target is to deliver a high quality part, the capability to monitor key process parameters as well as field variables and to detect critical evolution –taking into account their interdependencies- seems to be an important enabler for the industrialization of infusion process from practical point of view.